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The need for stepping into the battlefield of narratives: Countering the Chinese BRI narrative with Mausam and SAGAR

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Abstract

In the realm of foreign policy, the cognitive dimension plays a vital role. Yet its centrality to the conduct of international affairs seems to elude the Indian establishment. Arguing from this basic understanding that authoritarian China's meteoric rise implies troubles for India, the paper stresses the need to change India's traditional wait-and-watch approach to foreign policy, and that the battle of narratives be treated with due priority. China's narrative is reflected and propagated through its ambitious Belt & Road Initiative. India should build upon its SAGAR doctrine and Project Mausam to evolve an alternate narrative, and to develop it not just as a potential connectivity alternate to the BRI, but also an alternative paradigm in international relations

Keywords BRI, Project Mausam, Narrative, Indian foreign policy, China.

Introduction

Narrative in international relations

"Man is in his actions and practice, essentially a story telling man"- Alasdair Macintyre

Understood as the art of story-telling, narrative is perhaps as old as human existence. In systemic studies, narrative is understood as 'a representation of a particular situation or process in such a way as to reflect or conform to an overarching set of values.'¹ Patterson and Monroe understand narrative as how disparate facts are constructed and weaved together cognitively to make sense of reality, and since narratives help in shaping our political reality, it becomes important to understand it to gain a better understanding of political behaviour.²

Objective of study

The objective of this paper is to study the need for stepping into the battlefield of narratives in countering the Chinese BRI narrative with Mausam and SAGAR

Review of Literature

As per Foss, it is a way to portray a worldview by providing a description of various elements like characters, situations etc in a certain sequence like a story.³ Walter Fischer defines narration as a theory of symbolic actions- words and/or deeds – that have sequence and meaning for those who live, create or interpret them. Christening human beings as 'homo narrans', Fischer argues that man is a 'symbol using animal' and these symbols are ultimately communicated and created in the form of stories which give order to human experience and enable common living.⁴ In line with such understanding, narrative in the context of this paper is being understood as an overall cognitive framework which moulds how a casual observer would view actors and actions in

international relations. The decisions, actions and opinions of the observer as well as the participants will be affected by the larger narrative that is created and conveyed through careful choice of words, sentences, images etc.

Main Text

Leaders, nations, politicians make use of narrative to reach out to the people or audience. A good story which people can relate to, can inspire people into taking and/or supporting desired actions. For example, in most democracies, elections are a battle of narratives between the competing parties, where the story with the highest appeal to the people wins their votes. Individuals make sense of complex situations by creating a narrative in their heads. Where logical arguments cannot persuade a person, a story or narrative that 'makes-sense' can prove convincing.

Narratives play an important role in international politics. While it is true that several contradictory as well as complimentary narratives exist at the same time, some are more dominant, popular and widely accepted, or more normalized than others. What issues will be considered important for wider discussions, what language will be utilized to address a concern, etc are central to the conduct of international politics. Time and again the centrality of creation of appropriate narrative has been witnessed in world politics- British colonization, America's global war on terror, both camps in the Cold War, etc all made use of appropriate narrative building.

Narrative is a well-recognized and well-employed tool for conducting foreign relations, where it serves various purposes- First, it is a channel of communication in the international community. This is how nations convey the image of their selves as a country in the international community. It is to showcase the values a nation prioritizes; it is how it wants others to perceive it. Interactions with other actors in the international realm is guided to some extent by this narrative image.

Second, the narrative is not restricted to external sphere but is also directed towards domestic audience. Successful implementation of policies requires support from the domestic populace. Narrative helps mould and mobilize that support.

Third, the idea of narrative in international relations is closely linked with the concept of 'soft power' as enunciated by Joseph Nye. Nye states soft power as the ability of one country to get the other countries 'want' what it wants. A country can fulfil its national interests by virtue of other states following or agreeing to its agenda.⁵ Soft power lies in the capacity to shape others' preferences by setting the framework of debate. It lends legitimacy to foreign policy decisions and goals, and this legitimacy reduces resistance from others in a way coercive or hard power cannot attain.

The Chinese narrative of 'new kind of international relations' in light of Belt and Road Initiative (BRI)

Communism as an ideology is very partial towards use of propaganda. The present Chinese communist government is no different. The more than 72 years of history of the communist People's Republic of China is rife with instances when the state machinery has been successful in using narrative as a tool to motivate and mobilize its huge mass of people towards a goal (albeit the coercive state apparatus was simultaneously employed). The same tried and tested technique of story-telling and narration-building that the Chinese government has employed domestically is extended in its foreign policy. Even before the launch of BRI, Chinese official policy documents were already using a different language and tone, which was indicative of the change in the self-perception of the Chinese with regards to the role they saw themselves playing on the global stage. BRI simply marks the culmination of this changed perception in its self-assigned role, and its expression on the international platform.

Out of the many works on BRI produced from China and/or by Chinese authors that have been pursued by the researcher, speeches by high-ranking Chinese officials, etc it was observed that there is a remarkable degree of similarity in the arguments put forth, the terminology used, and an overall perception of affairs. There is a constant repetition of words like 'win-win cooperation', 'community of common destiny', 'partnership on equal footing', 'new era in international relations', 'shared benefits', 'genuine multilateralism' etc. The constant line of argument being pursued in all of these works is that unlike the 'West's' self-centred approach to national interests, China realizes that the ultimate long-term fulfilment of its national interests is dependent on the well-being of the other countries. Therefore, it seeks to share its prosperity and development-related wisdom with other developing or lesser/least developed nations. To enable the development of a community of shared future, wherein the different players engage with each other on equal footing and derive mutual benefits, there is a need to challenge and change the

currently dominant western way of conducting affairs in the international realm. The BRI is supposedly a demonstration of the practicality of this narrative.

BRI as actualization of an alternative narrative

Chinese narrative has been developed and presented as a contrast to the west dominated system of world politics, which the Chinese describe as being characterized by hierarchies, unending expansionism and domination-subjugation relations between the various actors. China's approach to international relations, as they portray it to be, is marked by some important departures from this present state of affairs dominated by USA and its allies. These departures, as asserted by Beijing are-

1. **Multi-polarity as against US-polarity** : Beijing has been at the forefront of the global North versus global South debate, and it has played its self-assigned role of being the leader of the developing world countries enthusiastically. China has been pretty outspoken in demanding total reformation of key international institutions so that they be more reflective of contemporary political realities. BRI is presented as a manifestation of this emphasis on multi-polarity. It encourages multi-polarity by challenging the developed world's dominance over international trade routes and trade related infrastructure by creating alternative routes, infrastructures, and finance and development related institutions. In this way the dependency of the developing world over the developed world reduces because the guiding principles of the 'new kind of international relations' as proposed by Beijing enhance partnership and cooperation amongst the developing countries.
2. **Non-interference as against violation of sovereignty** : Because China staunchly resists even the slightest interventions in its domestic issues, it constantly advocates the same treatment of other countries as well. This policy line is stressed to show a clear diversion from the interventionist foreign policy favoured by USA such as the War on Terror pretext used to intervene in Iraq, Syria, Afghanistan etc. Meddling with sovereignty also happens at a much subtle level when, for example, development projects funded by the global north are accompanied by demands for changes in economic and political structures of a country in need of funds. Participation in the development projects of BRI requires no such demands. Democracy or not, liberal society or not, China is willing to embrace them all as partners in this grand vision.
3. **Fairer financial regime as against 'Core' oriented institutions** : As an important part of the Chinese narrative of 'new' international relations, the need for egalitarian and fairer financial structures and institutions in the international realm is constantly underscored. The financial regime as it is at present is geared towards the goal of integrating the maximum number of countries into the capitalist economic system. Definite efforts are made to open the developing nations' fledgling markets for free trade, and democratic traits are strengthened. Financial crisis in a country is used as an advantage point to push forth market reforms and political changes. The core-periphery arrangement is preserved. For example, key lending institutions like IMF and World Bank impose several conditions on the borrowing state before extending loans, and these preconditions are geared towards making the borrower nation more liberal-democratic, more integrated with the capitalist world economic system.
4. China is right in calling out this prejudiced arrangement, and is using this to its own advantage for presenting its 'new international relations' as an alternative to this dominant-subject status quo by offering alternative financial arrangements. At one level the BRI is supposed to provides a solution to this predicament by integrating the poorer countries with the supply chains through development of infrastructure. Enhanced connectivity will be followed by an enhanced flow of goods, capital and technology which will empower the weaker nations on their path to development. Through alternate financial institutions like the Silk Road Fund, Asian Infrastructure Investment Bank, Belt and Road Special Lending Scheme, etc it is argued that China is lending economic voice to the smaller countries which otherwise have no say in the setting of rules of the international financial system.⁶
5. **Cooperation as against domination** : China has pressed forth the narrative of the contradiction between partnerships for mutual development which are marked by cooperation as against the characteristically 'ruler-ruled' tinged exploitative interactions of the west-dominant international regime. As the Chinese spokespersons keep stating, the BRI is a project which is based on the principle of 'partnership on equal footing'. This is very different from the development projects usually initiated by the West. Their projects are marked by an inequality- the divide between the rich and the poor countries is reflected in the terms of agreements of these projects and there is no equal partnership but domination-subjugation relationship. The signatory countries to the Chinese Initiative do not need to make structural adjustments in their internal economic or political systems in order to qualify for infrastructure development and granting of loans.
6. **Responsible development as against exploitative development** : Most of the major issues faced by the world today are direct results of self-centred and short-

sighted development trajectory undertaken by the developed world nations. The existential threat caused by climate change is a gift of uncontrolled industrial and urban expansion. The Chinese narrative of development is sufficiently aware of the need to address environmental concerns associated with large-scale development. To quote Xi speaking at the Second Belt and Road Forum – “it aims to promote green development. We may launch green infrastructure projects, make green investment and provide green financing to protect the Earth which we all call home.”⁷ Chinese experts claim on international forums that since the beginning of the BRI, the Chinese government has issued detailed guidelines for Chinese companies to promote green and sustainable development.⁸

The BRI narrative highlights all the aforementioned contrarities between the US dominated Western international regime and the ‘new international relations’ with Chinese characteristics guided by Chinese wisdom. The launch of this initiative and its uptake by a large number of countries, according to the Chinese experts, represents the beginning of a ‘new era’ in international relations which is marked by trust, cooperation, meaningful partnerships and mutual development. To quote from the 2015 vision and action document for BRI, the Silk Road Spirit is made of “peace and cooperation, openness and inclusiveness, mutual learning and mutual benefit”, and serves the purpose of bringing prosperity and development to the countries which are a part of it, and the larger goal of promotion of the progress of human civilization.⁹

SAGAR and Project Mausam- Developing an alternate narrative

India’s foreign policy has been traditionally focused towards its territorial frontiers which is understandable given its troublesome border relations with some of the neighbours. However, ignoring the Indian Ocean region, the heart of world trade, has been an undefendable blunder. India is geographically positioned in a highly advantageous position in the Indian Ocean, but it has not utilized it much, either in the strategic or the cultural sense. Now, in the context of the larger picture of the USA-China Cold War, the Indian ocean has become the centre of attention. China wishes to increase its presence in the region to protect its expanding vital interests and for power projection. To that end it is pushing forward the Maritime Silk Road Initiative part of BRI. India is rightly wary of the growing Chinese interest and presence in the region. The Chinese initiative has acted as an impetus for India taking a more pro-active interest in the ocean, one result of which is the SAGAR doctrine and Project Mausam.

SAGAR is an acronym for ‘Security And Growth for All in the Region’. It was first referenced to by the Indian PM in 2015 while commissioning CGS Baracuda. The Indian establishment hasn’t been very forthcoming in enunciating the exactitudes of it. It has been variously referred to as vision, doctrine, policy and concept. Project Mausam was first introduced in 2014 at the 38th World Heritage session at Doha. It has been put forth as a project under the Ministry of Culture, and its main objective is to inscribe places and sites identified under Project Mausam as trans-national nomination for UNESCO’s World Heritage List. The stated aim of the project is at two levels- at the macro level, to re-connect and re-establish communications between countries of the Indian Ocean world, which would lead to an enhanced understanding of cultural values and concerns. At the micro level, the focus is on understanding national cultures in their regional maritime milieu.^{10,11}

Because India has been linked with the Indian Ocean littoral countries for centuries, the cultural overlaps, and relations run deep. Through Project Mausam these traditionally vital relations can be revived and revitalized. The creation of a narrative that views the Indian Ocean Region (IOR) as a composite neighbourhood has immense potential, not just in terms of geo-strategic foreign policy but also with reference to the huge benefits that can be accrued from blue economy.

India is not the only country that is uneasy with increasing Chinese footprints in this ocean. When India showcases a definite intention through the building and propagation of a proper narrative, other actors and stakeholders in the region and those with a vision for the Indian Ocean Region- governments, organizations other than governments, private actors, individuals, and public at large will come together. This evidenced in India recently gaining the membership of two important IOR forums, the Indian Ocean Rim Association and Indian Ocean Commission. When it comes to the Indian Ocean region, China’s only major advantage is the huge size of its economy. On the other hand, India has the benefit of geography, and also China’s belligerence has made other stakeholders eager to find ways to balance its increasing influence- India is the only viable option. China realizes the potential of the SAGAR doctrine and Mausam. It is why Beijing has blocked its acceptance as Heritage by UNESCO, clearly stating the reason that it would be detrimental for its MSRI.¹²

India should not seek to counter BRI with similarly imagined and structured projects. The answer should be a real alternative, actually based on mutuality and cosmopolitanism. China is seeking to dominate the global commons, India should not answer with similar strategy, even while seeking to prevent infringement of its national interests. Even in responding to China, India should choose her own template, instead of adopting a reactionary, tit-for-tat kind of narrative building. The contradictions and shortfalls of the western system are visible for everyone to see. The Chinese system is facing backlash and resentment even before it could gain requisite recognition. The present state when the 'established' is no longer enough for humanity and search for alternative paradigm is on, India should step in to fill the philosophical vacuum.

Viewing the world from realism's perspective does not have to preclude the possibility of actual cooperation among nations without such attempts precipitating into being a mere playground for power politics. This is not to say that security and strategic concerns, or power politics can be wished away or separated from international initiatives, but that the hawkish tendencies need not take centre stage. The possibility of successful cooperation is exemplified to some extent by the European Union. To a large extent, meaningful cooperation is dependent on finding appropriate common ground. Sea Lines of Open Communications, trade through the Indian Ocean, benefits of robust blue economy, commonalities in culture, shared history and shared concern for safety, stability and openness of global commons (here, the Indian Ocean)– these are compelling reasons for coming together. Owing to geography, and because of the quintessential 'Indianness' of its being, India is the one country which can make such cooperation a possibility. Mausam has to be built organically, not forcefully like BRI. Only then will it be long lasting, sustainable, and garner more and real partners.

Way forward for India

First, initiate larger discussions about India's position in the Indian Ocean, both domestically and internationally. Project Mausam SAGAR and other related issues should be a part of the mainstream discussions, at least domestically in India. While the desirability of following China's way of conducting foreign policy is undoubtedly questionable, India should definitely learn a thing or two from it. For example, with the launching of MSRI, China suddenly rediscovered (and reinvented) Admiral Zheng He. Both USA and China have utilized popular media as platforms for propagating desired narratives, from John Rambo to Ip Man. Indian history is full of legendary stories of sages, rulers, travellers, dynasties that should be worked upon and made part of common domestic narrative at least, to begin with; stories about the Spice Route, the Cholas in south east Asia- stories that span the entire Indian Ocean region. Buddhism and Chola kingdom are in fact being prepared for transnational nomination under Mausam.¹³

Second, fund research on the various aspects of SAGAR and Mausam- benefits and limitations, the historical and cultural ties between the Indian Ocean nations, and the central position that India had enjoyed in major trade routes, both in sea and overland. Quality research is the first requisite step towards creation of a narrative, and for making informed foreign policy.

Third, expand the scope of Project Mausam. Even if it is only a cultural project, its goals have been defined in such limited terms that a casual observer might view it as a minor initiative which will gather dust over time, as yet another half-hearted attempt by India to assert its position in its own area of influence. It runs the risk of becoming another potentially brilliant idea not realized because of lethargy and extreme unease with rubbing any country the wrong way, even when it could cost vital long term national interests.

Some recent government initiatives showcase India's slow but steady steps towards creating its own Indian ocean narrative. For example, in 2023, the Culture ministry and Navy signed an MoU to revive the ancient Tankai shipbuilding method, and a ship thus built will sail along the ancient maritime trade routes in the Indian Ocean to bring to fore India's maritime heritage and cultural relations with Indian Ocean rim nations. In 2022, the Archaeological Survey of India (ASI), which is in charge of overseeing Project Mausam, organized a conference to explore cross-cultural linkages along the Indian Ocean nations, with ambassadors and other dignitaries of the Indian Ocean rim countries. Lahiri and others also hail the stitched-ship project as an attempt to regain maritime identity.^{14, 15}

Fourth, develop holistic, long-term vision for India's place in the international community over the years to come. When this happens, fragmented and seemingly haphazard policies as Look East, Link West, Spice route etc will streamline and can assume a

totality of meaning and character. The 21st century is called Asia's century, and India should have a clear idea of its role in this century.

Conclusion

The latent potential of Project Mausam can be gleaned from the fact that China has blocked the World Heritage status for it, stating that it would be detrimental for its MSRI, even though it is only a cultural project. That is because Beijing understands and makes ample use of the tool of narrative. The power of language and words cannot be overstated. It is literally how human beings perceive the world. There is a famous Native American proverb- 'Those who tell the stories, rule the world'. India has somehow always lagged behind in the battle of narratives. For example- despite being the victim in the Kashmir dispute, India is always on the defensive when the issue is raised in international forums. The fact that Pakistan and China are able to use it to pressurize India, even though it is they who have occupied Indian sovereign territory attests to the role narratives play in international relations. Narrative is how China justified its occupation of Tibet, an issue that never got its due recognition on any international platform. The terminologies used in international narratives have a huge impact on shaping the framework of perceptions and relationships among nations. For instance, the simple act of USA switching to the use of the term 'Indo-Pacific' instead of 'Asia Pacific' drew loud responses from China, because it has brought India and Indian Ocean to the centre of the framework. In recent years, China has raised objections at the nomenclature of the Indian Ocean, and has often acidly pointed out that Indian Ocean is not India's Ocean.

It would be unfair to assume that Indian foreign policy is static or that its policy makers are unaware of what is brewing in their backyard, because certain changes have been visible, especially since the change of government in 2014. Moving over its past hesitations, India has joined the Quad. It has launched the International Solar Alliance. In face of the raging Wuhan virus pandemic, India launched Mission Sagar in 2020 for providing Covid related assistance to Indian Ocean region countries. There is ample use of terms like 'Vasudhaiv Kutumbakam', 'Satyamev Jayate', etc in international platforms which are representative of the Indian ethos. As the devouring dragon tears through the cute panda façade of China, India is pitching its narrative as a story of stable growth, open and tolerant society.

But New Delhi is not as forthcoming in its foreign policy yet as it should perhaps be, and one of the reasons for this has been that India has always sought to avoid tensions with China. The wait-and-watch policy had its merits but now that the theatre of world politics and major action has shifted from Europe and Atlantic, right into our neighbourhood, dillydallying is costing us allies. The lack of a coherent vision for India in the decades to come results in lack of comprehensive policy making and implementation in short term. India's intellectual and political leaders need to ponder over this basic question- how will it justify its self-proclaimed role of 'Vishwa-Guru' when it lags in understanding and discussing its own affairs. India was the central hub of the ancient Silk Road, and because of India's nonchalance to use of narratives, the silk route has been entirely appropriated by the Chinese. Spice Route might meet a similar fate. India needs targeted focus on creating its own narrative in the Indian Ocean region, and SAGAR and Project Mausam are the initial steps in the right direction.

The issue at hand is not just India's complex relations with China or the race to dominate Indian Ocean. The larger issue is the lack of sustainable guiding principles in international relations and world affairs. The currently dominant paradigm is heavily guided by the modernist understanding of human beings as self-interested individuals which results in conception of nation states as power hungry entities forever locked in domination-subjugation pattern. The modernist narrative of ever-expanding development (common to both capitalist and socialist/communist frameworks) is responsible for the current state of affairs- the struggle for power, grabbing of natural resources, the precipitating environmental crisis and the associated loss of life. India's unique philosophical traditions can provide an alternative paradigm that is truly sustainable and humanity-centred. India must seek to be a superpower, but it should seek alternative ways of achieving it, instead of following the set pattern, which has proven itself to be unsustainable and inadequate.

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